

Towards coherent experiences: tools to understand and orchestrate the elements of an experience

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Abstract This paper introduces six tools which we developed in a real project. They help the designer to understand the elements of an existing experience and then to change, extend or build an experience. The demand for such tools became apparent in a cooperative project with a car manufacturer who struggles with a 'lack of uniqueness'. The interior design and especially the cockpit have become less characteristic compared to former models. The aim of the tools is to support the design of a more coherent experience. That requires: avoiding disappointing moments, creating coherence in the perception of the cars, and building extraordinary the right reminiscences to bring back the uniqueness of a product.

Key words design tools, methods, experience design, cognitive dissonance, brand, touchpoints, congruency, strategy

Introduction

This paper introduces six tools and a design language. The tools support the designer to understand an experience by deconstructing it: into its elements, their relations, and their emotion eliciting conditions. The tools synthesize knowledge from the sciences. And as sciences often have specific terminologies a design language emerged from the synthesis as a generalized way to speak about the elements of an experience.

This paper builds upon a thesis which was conducted in cooperation with a car manufacturer. The initial design brief was concerned with a 'lack of uniqueness' in the cockpit of the car. This is a general problem of products that are similar in respect to their technical characteristics, quality and price and therefore offer fewer reasons to prefer one. While the car as a whole is technologically well developed it lacks significant characteristics to express the brand and thus offers an increasingly interchangeable experience with competing products.

The cockpit should serve as a stage to experience the brand through the use of the car. Appropriate characteristics need to invigorate the experience of the car. Businesses demand such differentiation through all touchpoints to express their brands (Suri, 2004).

The problem of lacking uniqueness can be found at many levels of a car design e.g. for a button in the cockpit of the car: How shall this button be designed to resonate with the whole car and to resemble its core qualities appropriately? How shall the button feel, click, sound, move? This is one instance of a general problem: How can the design of a total (product) experience be guided through all its elements to fit in with the product at large?

Reason for the insignificance of products is an increased number of possibilities. Technological advancements offer new materials and new ways of manufacturing to create different qualities of touch, behaviour, or shape. Product characteristics are less bound to mechanical restrictions as they become smaller, digital, and electrical – they now can resemble a wide range of characteristics. This increased number of possible characteristics complicates the choice – which one is the right one? This development coincides with an increasing demand for product features – which require additional design decisions in the development of a product. The more design decisions are to be made the more effort it takes to align the decisions to result in a convincing total experience. This paper documents our efforts in improving the orchestration of design decisions to build a coherent experience more strategically and in a reproducible way.

The term 'coherence' shall not be misunderstood as the intent to 'streamline' an experience. A product's perception does not solely consist of pleasurable emotions. As stated by van der Veen and Illman (2004) this approach is too narrow. A 'pleasure principle' of product interaction needs to include more than just positive emotions to support a rewarding experience. Even 'paradoxical emotions' – as a simultaneous combination of positive and negative emotions – can be desirable (Desmet quoting Frijda, 2004).

To describe the coherence of a product's perception we refer to the 'cognitive dissonance' theory by Leon Festinger (1953). According to cognitive dissonance theory, there is a tendency for individuals to seek consistency among their cognitions because dissonance is presumed as uncomfortable. Dissonance might result when an individual must choose between attitudes and behaviours that are contradictory.

Although we dislike putting it vague: It depends on the product's 'essence' which blend of characteristics is appropriate and perceived as coherent. Driving e.g. a Porsche – especially a former model – can be very demanding with no easy steering and only little suspension, but it is exactly this experience that one seeks and expects. The same experience in another car is probably disappointing.

Coherence is in the perception of a product. This perception refers to the idea that a customer creates in her mind when interacting with a product or a service (see, hear, touch, think of, etc.). It is a result of all those little interactions (which we call 'touchpoints').

Experiences cannot be crafted because experiences are subjective perceptions (Forlizzi, 2000). When a product elicits an emotion, it is induced by a specific product-subject relationship within a specific context. According to Lazarus (1991) the conditions that elicit emotions are universal. Understanding these conditions may improve the design towards a desired experience. Designers influence the quality of interactions and in this way affect people's perception. They can increase the probability of a desired perception.

We are aware that with safety-critical products like cars, it is the responsibility of the designer to ensure that the functionality is safe to use. Balancing the cognitive situation in a car requires thinking about crucial driving routines first and only then to include further levels of the driving experience to be designed for positive affect (Summerskill, Burnett, 2002).

In the case of driving a car the behavioural aspects are the immediate expectations, and when those are always fulfilled, the driver feels to be in control, resulting in positive affect. If the car does not appear to respond as commanded, this leads to negative affect. Emotions can, furthermore, arise on the visceral and reflective level i.e. being pleased by watching or owning an object. Such positive affect can increase the motivation to master an object and to tolerate minor flaws (Norman, 2004).

Tools

The developed tools fall in two categories: evaluative and generative. The *Circumplex Model*, the *Material Survey*, the *Phases of Use*, the *Clustering*, and the *Particle Watch* help deconstructing and understanding the elements of an experience. They reveal connections, patterns and priorities. The generative tool is: The *Touchpoint Equalizer*. It merges the insights from the evaluative tools and supports the experiences' orchestration.

Circumplex Model

Early in the project the necessity did arise to 'get a grip' on the involved emotions of an experience, as far as they became apparent. This was a first step to consider emotions in the design of experiences. A visual representation would reduce the intangibility of the emotions and support their discussion.

We use an adaptation of the circumplex model of affect (Watson & Tellegen, 1985) to capture the emotions elicited throughout an experience. This utilisation corresponds with the original pursuit of the model: Evaluating how many different emotions exist based on empiric dimensions. The model is robust and characterizes affect at a general level. The models' weakness is its sometimes indifferent handling of emotions as the model suggests some familiarity between emotions that are significantly different, like between hate and fear. It is, nevertheless, discussed, modified and used since its initial publication in 1902 by Wilhelm Wundt which indicates some validity to us.

A comparable tool – called 'emotion wheel' – was developed at the University of Geneve for the verbal report of emotional reactions. The descriptive power of this tool is only limited by the ambiguity of language. Different people might associate different emotions with the same attributes or vice versa (Tanja Bänziger, 2005). Once an emotion is annotated in the

circumplex model its allocation along the dimensions (valence, arousal) allows for some validation on the shared understanding of the verbalized emotion.

We observed that a set of product emotions annotated in the model make up a pattern. These patterns resemble a set of emotions that result from a user-product relation. This pattern has some descriptive power and could be used as 'profile' to describe or distinguish a brand experience.

Figure 1 Sketch of the adapted Circumplex Model

Material Survey

Another tool for exploring the emotions in a user-product relationship is the *Material Survey*. With focus on the relation between emotions and the haptic perception of a material we carried out a test. The research question was: Do different people associate similar emotions with the same material?

Twenty-two materials were tested e.g. different kinds of wood, plastics, textiles and rubber. Participants were not able to see the material but could only touch it. There were no time-constraints. The test was carried out in two phases. The first phase was conducted with four participants to test and refine the test.

The second phase was conducted with twelve participants including the refinements and additions from the first phase. While the first phase used multiple choice questions the second phase used scaled questions with a semantic differential and fewer attributes. This sped up the test and was beneficial to the participant's concentration because one session (one participant evaluating all materials) had an average duration of one hour.

Initially the participants progressed only slowly but soon the associations were drawn easier. The default attributes on the questionnaire were appreciated by the participants and triggered the addition of custom attributes.

As this survey was supposed to be a quick research it will not be presented in detail. Basically the results of the survey indicate a tendency among the perceptions and associations about the emotional qualities of materials. For most materials the participants predominantly associated a similar emotion. Rarely the cumulated associations did not show a clear tendency. We don't conclude an unambiguous relation between materials and emotions but we see reason to consider the results as criterion to choose one material.

The blind evaluation of the materials corresponds with driving situations where materials are predominantly touched but not looked at e.g. steering, shifting, adjusting the volume. Nevertheless it would be of value to repeat the test with more participants and a separate visual evaluation of the materials.

Figure 2 Blind evaluation of materials on a correlation of their haptic qualities and emotions

Phases of Use

Apart from the emotional dimensions we applied a simple technique to deconstruct existing experiences to deepen our understanding. We subdivided an experience in *Phases of Use*. This segmentation is done alongside the encounter and use of something. We subdivided the use of a car into seven phases: Out of sight, approach, open and enter, initiate, drive, stop and shutdown, leave. The needs and expectations towards the car differ throughout the phases. The granularity of the divisions is variable. Irregular phases should also be regarded e.g. buying or maintaining a car. Some phases are extensive and can be subdivided repeatedly while others only are short. It depends largely on the nature of the experience.

Breaking down the complete experience into single phases assists in understanding transitions that shape the experience e.g. change of speed, change of the social configuration (individual,

group), transitions between dominating levels of perception (behavioural, reflective, or visceral), transitions between the mode of contact (touch it, or think of it), etc.

It is, nevertheless, worthwhile to systematically break down the experience and to not stick with obvious distinctions. A deep-dive for inherent distinctive patterns is inspirational as an experience becomes de-centred from its obvious characteristics and reveals more subtle relations.

Tom Kelley (2005) from IDEO already recommended following your customers' journey, breaking it down into its component elements, and asking yourself how you can deliver a better experience. Nathan Shedroff argues that superior experiences are reproducible and also recommends deconstructing an experience to analyse, and to ultimately design it (2001).

Clustering

While the phases of use assist in deconstructing the general experience we also deconstructed the physical elements of an experience. The object of our investigation was the cockpit of a car. This means we started at a given experience and did not create one from scratch.

We identified all pieces of the cockpit and created a taxonomy with pictures, descriptions, functions, and the corresponding contexts (e.g. door, steering, seat, air condition). In addition to this basic description we related each element to a *Phase of Use* and clustered it according to its relevance e.g. driving-related, information-related, safety-related, convenience-related, and 'potential to become a reminiscence'. Furthermore, for each element we identified the mode of interaction (none, touch, turn, grab, press, push, pull, open, close, kick) and the mode of perception (visual, haptic, acoustical). The 'reminiscence' category applies for elements that carry a noteworthy meaning in this experience e.g. throttle, break, the button to open the convertible. These elements might be well-suited to be 'staged'. A similar approach can be found from Pine and Gillmore (2002) who demand that companies must 'stage experiences' and 'guide transformations' to establish differentiation.

The clustering is a tool to reveal patterns and particularities on the level of the tangible elements by analysing and categorizing them. The clustering has two major advantages i.e. the tangibility of the displayed elements is helpful to draw in people with a less conceptual approach and to subsequently introduce more complex relations. This way the clustering starts from known things to discover new things. The second advantage of the clustering is the decontextualization of the elements of an experience which allows for different perspective.

Particle Watch

The visualization of the elements of an experience is crucial in the understanding, discussing and designing of an experience. For this reason the *Particle Watch* offers an additional visual representation of the clustering: A circle, divided clockwise by the *Phases of Use* and the relevancy of the elements as categorizations on the sub circles (driving, information, safety, and convenience).

Figure 3 This Particle Watch correlates the elements of a car’s cockpit with the Phases of Use

The *ParticleWatch* assists in identifying the importance of elements in each *Phase of Use*. The distribution of elements according to their categories can be observed e.g. the numerous presence of convenience-related elements throughout the whole experience or the cumulation of safety-relevant elements in the driving phase.

Furthermore, this decontextualized representation (as it is detached from the actual cockpit layout) offers an alternative angle on the tangible pieces of the experience. Here the focus is on relation and distribution rather than on actual allocation.

Touchpoint Equalizer (TPEQ)

The tools introduced so far focus on deconstructing or decontextualizing the experience to support its understanding. The Touchpoint Equalizer aims on recontextualizing those insights. The *TPEQ* is a matrix that is horizontally divided by the *Phases of Use* and vertically divided by the states of cognitive dissonance or consonance. The *TPEQ* supports the designer in staging the experience as it allows for a coordinated orchestration of the elements. It supports the exploration of opportunities and priorities. The *TPEQ* is scalable. It can be used for short and extended experiences. And it can be applied for very different experiences as it makes use of a universal way of representing an experience through its touchpoints.

First step in using the *TPEQ* is collecting touchpoints. This collection does not have to be exhaustive to start using the *TPEQ* but it gains momentum the more compelling it is. To guide the collection of touchpoints we observe customer journeys. An accumulation of touchpoints from several customer journeys indicates a touchpoint that might be worth prioritizing design actions on.

The touchpoints are horizontally distributed according to their *Phase of Use*. Their vertical position is regulated by their degree of consonance. While the dissonant area is at the bottom, the median represents the consonant area and above the median are touchpoints that exceed expectations.

Figure 4 The Touchpoint Equalizer visualizes an experience along its touchpoints

Sociology of Touchpoints

To decide whether and where action is required you need to compare the existing state of the experience with the desired one in the *TPEQ*. From our observations a good first strategy is to decrease the existing dissonance as it is perceived as uncomfortable. But if ‘uncomfortable’ belongs to the script of your desired experience then do stage this characteristic in ways that it is valued for. If a dissonance cannot be eliminated at all it might be a good strategy to add or strengthen positive touchpoints as a counterbalance. This decreases the probability of only negative aspects to be remembered.

These recommendations for the manipulation of touchpoints are hypothetical. They belong to the *Sociology of Touchpoints* which is a set of generalized observations about the ‘mechanisms’ of touchpoints which is under development:

- **Negative touchpoints are more heavy than positive ones.** The discomfort of dissonant cognitions seems to outweigh the cognition of consonant elements in an experience.
- **Every touchpoint counts.** It cannot be predicted which parts of an experience are perceived and the human mind tends to ‘interpolate’ limited information to create a picture that is mistakenly taken as complete.
- **Touchpoints can team up.** A consecutive series of touchpoints that are perceived as positive might reinforce each other to become a perception that exceeds the impacts of the single touchpoints.
- **Touchpoints are radioactive.** A touchpoint can alter the perception of subsequent touchpoints (positively or negatively). The perception of whole experiences is affected by preceding experiences.
- **Disappointments are unavoidable.** The perception of an experience cannot be controlled. It is not possible to prevent every dissonant encounter. Some perceptions can only be made less or more probable.

Conclusion

We believe that science can inform design in more than just explanatory or descriptive ways. Our objective is to provide tools for the design profession that synthesize scientific knowledge to guide the design process through to the generative level. In this respect the paper showcases a ‘scientific design’ process where scientific knowledge is applied to think and work towards a solution with a mix of intuitive and non-intuitive design methods (Cross, 1999). Interestingly the described design process is self-referential in that it utilizes design to improve the design process itself.

The tools mainly work by deconstructing and reconstructing an experience with consideration of emotional issues. First, their mere visual power helps establishing a shared vision, in prioritizing actions, and in making the emotional aspects of an experience more tangible.

Second, the tools aim at synchronizing design decisions with an underlying concept (e.g. a brand) to make the touchpoints resonate with the total experience and thus support a desired perception. Third, the tools build on psychological theories and observations. They include knowledge about emotions and their eliciting conditions. Although emotions are ultimately subjective phenomena and very ambiguous some of the insights might offer guidance in an otherwise often arbitrary (and emotion-blind) design process.

The *Sociology of Touchpoints* is a first step towards an experience design language. Its main goal is a unified and applicable way to deal with the design of a total experience.

Through the development of the tools and the necessary research we achieved some literacy on the involved topics which we experienced as an advantage in other design projects.

We see further research as required for ...

- the measurability of touchpoints and their level of consonance/dissonance.
- the ‘Sociology of Touchpoints’ to become actionable
- more empirical data on the relation of emotions and materials

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